

Synthesis of 3-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -lactosylimino-4-aryl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrochlorides)

P. V. Tale and S. P. Deshmukh*

P. G. Department of Chemistry, Shri Shivaji College, Akola-444 001, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : prashanttale@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : Some 3-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -lactosylimino-4-aryl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrochlorides) (3) have been synthesized for the first time involving interaction of 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides (1) and *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (2).

Keywords : Substituted dithiazolidines, β -lactosyl compounds, thiocarbamides.

The *N*-lactosylated compounds have several applications in industry and also in medicinal chemistry¹. We have recently prepared 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides by the interaction of hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl isothiocyanate and aryl amines². In view of our interest in *N*-lactosylated cyclic compounds, we now report the synthesis of 3-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -lactosylimino-4-aryl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrochlorides) (3).

Results and discussion

The reaction of 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-phenyl thiocarbamide (1a) and *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloroisothiocarbamoyl chloride (2) was carried out in dry CHCl₃ for 3 h on boiling water bath. After condensation the solvent CHCl₃ was distilled off and sticky mass was isolated as residue. This when triturated several times with petroleum ether was converted to a granular pale yellow solid (3a) crystallised from ethanol-water, m.p. 155 °C. The product was found to be non-desulfurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. The specific rotation was found to be $[\alpha]_D^{32} + 51.65^\circ$ (*c*, 0.968 in CHCl₃). The purity of product was checked by TLC and recorded *R_f* value 0.46. Its IR spectrum³ shows bands at λ_{\max} 3024 (Ar-H), 1753 (C=O), 1612 (C=N), 1587 (Ar-C=C), 1369 (C-N), 1228 (C-O), 1051 and 906 (characteristics of lactose), 754 (C-S), 696 (monosubstituted benzene ring). Its ¹H NMR spectrum⁴ (CDCl₃) displayed signals due to aromatic protons 6.83–7.56 (10H, m), lactose unit proton were located at 3.72–5.29 (14H, m) and signal due to -COCH₃ located at 1.96–2.17 (21H, m). Its mass spectrum⁵ display peaks at *m/z*, 976 (M⁺), 904, 769, 620, 331, 169 (base peak), 109.

On the basis of all the above facts, the structure of the

product with m.p. 155 °C was assigned as 3-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -lactosylimino-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (hydrochlorides) (3a).

The reaction of *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloroisothiocarbamoyl chloride (2) was extended to several other substituted 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-arylthiocarbamides (1b-g) and the corresponding products (3b-g) were isolated (Table 1).

Table 1. 3-Hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -lactosylimino-4-aryl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrochlorides) (3)

Sl. no.	Compd. (g)	Compd. (g)	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	$[\alpha]_D^{32}$ CHCl ₃	<i>R_f</i> value
1.	1a (2.4)	3a (2.3)	75.6	155	+51.65° (<i>c</i> , 0.968)	0.46
2.	1b (2.4)	3b (1.9)	62.7	169	+29.76° (<i>c</i> , 1.008)	0.87
3.	1c (2.4)	3c (1.6)	52.8	197	+56.81° (<i>c</i> , 1.056)	0.62
4.	1d (2.4)	3d (1.9)	62.7	188	+80.97° (<i>c</i> , 0.988)	0.54
5.	1e (2.5)	3e (1.8)	57.3	138	+94.33° (<i>c</i> , 1.060)	0.85
6.	1f (2.5)	3f (1.8)	57.3	152	+77.51° (<i>c</i> , 1.032)	0.86
7.	1g (2.5)	3g (1.9)	54.1	136	+60.00° (<i>c</i> , 1.000)	0.47

Scheme 1

Experimental

The required *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloroisoithiocarbamoyl chloride (2) was prepared by known method⁶.

3-Hepta-O-acetyl-β-lactosylimino-4-phenyl-5-phenyl-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrochlorides) (3a) :

A chloroform solution *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloroisoithiocarbamoyl chloride (2) (0.003 *M*, 0.61 g) was mixed with chloroform solution of 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl-β-*D*-lactosyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide (1a-g) (0.003 *M*, 2.3 g) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h. After refluxing the solvent was distilled off and the resultant syrupy mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C). When a pale yellow solid (2.3 g) was obtained which was crystallized from ethanol-water (3a), m.p. 155 °C (Found : C, 49.00; H, 4.47; N, 4.21; S, 6.48. C₄₀H₄₅O₁₇N₃S₂·2HCl Calcd. for : C, 49.18; H, 4.61; N, 4.30; S, 6.55%).

(3b) : IR : 3020 (Ar-H), 1751 (C=O), 1591 (C=N), 1372 (C-N), 1228 (C-O), 1051 and 906 cm⁻¹ (characteristic of lactose); ¹H NMR δ : 1.68–2.24 (21H, m, 7-COCH₃), 2.55 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 3.74–5.37 (14H, m, lactose unit), 6.85–7.31 ppm (9H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 49.45; H, 4.51; N, 4.02; S, 6.24. C₄₁H₄₇O₁₇N₃S₂·2HCl Calcd. for : C, 49.69; H, 4.74; N, 4.24; S, 6.46%).

(3c) : IR : 3020 (Ar-H), 1751 (C=O), 1593 (C=N), 1372 (C-N), 1229 (C-O), 1051 and 906 cm⁻¹ (characteristic of lactose); ¹H NMR δ : 1.63–2.16 (21H, m, 7-COCH₃), 2.41 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 3.82–5.36 (14H, m, lactose unit), 7.14–7.49 ppm (9H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 49.52, H, 4.66; N, 4.10; S, 6.28. C₄₁H₄₇O₁₇N₃S₂·2HCl Calcd. for : C, 49.69; H, 4.74; N, 4.24; S, 6.46%).

(3d) : IR : 3024 (Ar-H), 1753 (C=O), 1608 (C=N), 1585 (C=C-Ar), 1369 (C-N), 1228 (C-O), 1049 and 908 (characteristic of lactose), 817 (1,4-disubstituted benzene), 756 (C-S), 696 cm⁻¹ (monosubstituted benzene); ¹H NMR δ : 1.97–2.17 (21H, m, 7-COCH₃), 2.40 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 3.72–5.32 (14H, m, lactose unit), 7.13–7.44 ppm (9H, m, Ar-H). Mass spectrum *m/z*, 992 (M+2)⁺, 976, 919, 784 (base peak), 620, 331, 169 (Found : C, 49.58; H, 4.70; N, 4.25; S, 6.10. C₄₁H₄₇O₁₇N₃S₂·2HCl Calcd. for : C, 49.69; H, 4.74; N, 4.24; S, 6.46%).

(3e) : IR : 3020 (Ar-H), 1753 (C=O), 1612 (C=N), 1589 (C=C-Ar), 1369 (C-N), 1217 (C-O), 1058 and 910 (characteristic of lactose), 756 cm⁻¹ (C-S, 1,2-disubstituted benzene); ¹H NMR δ : 1.96–2.14 (21H, m, 7-COCH₃), 3.72–5.30 (14H, m, lactose unit), 6.84–7.50 ppm (9H, m, Ar-H). Mass spectrum *m/z*, 1012 (M+2)⁺, 939 (base peak), 620, 331, 169, 109 (Found : C, 47.32; H, 4.24; N, 4.12; S, 5.97. C₄₀H₄₄O₁₇N₃S₂Cl₂·2HCl Calcd. for : C, 47.47; H, 4.35; N, 4.15; S, 6.33%).

(3f) : IR : 3020 (Ar-H), 1751 (C=O), 1597 (C=N), 1372 (C-N), 1230 (C-O), 1050 and 906 cm⁻¹ (characteristic of lactose); ¹H NMR δ : 1.68–2.15 (21H, m, 7-COCH₃), 3.75–5.35 (14H, m, lactose unit), 6.87–7.67 ppm (9H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 47.19; H, 4.15; N, 4.04; S, 6.13. C₄₀H₄₄O₁₇N₃S₂Cl₂·2HCl Calcd. for : C, 47.47; H, 4.35; N, 4.15; S, 6.33%).

(3g) : IR : 3020 (Ar-H), 1751 (C=O), 1597 (C=N), 1372 (C-N), 1230 (C-O), 1050 and 906 cm⁻¹ (characteristic of lactose); ¹H NMR δ : 1.69–2.17 (21H, m, 7-COCH₃), 3.77–5.36 (14H, m, lactose unit), 6.83–7.57 ppm (9H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 47.20; H, 4.09; N, 3.94; S, 6.19. C₄₀H₄₄O₁₇N₃S₂Cl₂·2HCl Calcd. for : C, 47.47; H, 4.35; N, 4.15; S, 6.33%).

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